

**BUSINESS GROWTH IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA
FOR 2008-2018 PERIOD**

Roxana Barb, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences,
Vienna, Austria

The paper presents the importance of the business growth in the mountain area, specific in the Romanian mountain area. The importance of this indicator has relevance in the development of the Romanian economy at systemic level. The sustainability of Romanian mountain area has an increased level of entropy, but through negentropy the system should be more organized and developed: "negentropy is not just a continuous ascent curve. In many cases, negentropy is survival..." (Covaci Mihai, Covaci Brîndușa, 2023, Negentropy: a sustainable culture of educational leadership. An OCAI model analysis)

Regarding the indicator which show the business growth in an area, *Net business growth – percent*, the statistics present an important evolution in the mountain area.

The related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to

Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentiles 25, 50, 75, so 6.2130, 5.53968, 2.1250, 17.51801, 306.881, 2.693, .687, 8.044, 1.334, 64.13, -10.02, 54.11, -2.753, 5750, 5750 .

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeat in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared 8.074E-17, 2.632E-16, -4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; R-squared 8.074E-17, 2.632E-16, -4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; RMSE 30,416, 33,057, 8,546, 122,092, 8,546, 8,986; MAPS 1245,735, 2965,953, 131,702, 10149,373, 131,702, 132,869; MaxAPE 10735.791, 29522.715, 432.621, 99440.000, 432.621, 450.004; MAE 18,016, 18,358, 6,070, 68,449, 6,070, 6,226; MaxAE 81,220, 94,473, 15,224, 342,243, 15,224, 17,045; Normalized BIC 6.379, 1.574, 4.521, 9.840, 4.521, 4.613.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I14 (values presented in the following order - Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 17.518 , 305,387, 10,041; S2-Model_2: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 10.746, 372.670, 7.068; S3-Model_3: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 11.240, 245.433, 6.070; S4-Model_4: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 12.842, 330.932, 8.778; S5-Model_5: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 17.715, 137.540, 9.817; S6-Model_6: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 8.546, 182.690, 6.853; S7-Model_7: .000, .000, 22,953, 131,702, 13,553; S8-Model_8: .000, .000, 22,130, 269,481, 15,592; S9-Model_9: .000, .000, 36,084, 10149,373, 20,032; S10-Model_10: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 122.092, 442.251, 68.449; S11-Model_11: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 52.713, 1135.631, 31.921.

Table 31. Prediction analysis for I14

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42
	UCL	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73
	LCL	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60
	UCL	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53
	LCL	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	17.05	14.90	12.74	10.59	8.44	6.29	4.14	1.99
	UCL	26.89	24.93	22.96	20.99	19.02	17.05	15.07	13.09

	LCL	7.20	4.86	2.52	.19	-2.14	-4.47	-6.79	-9.12
S4-	Forecast	16.09	15.16	14.23	13.30	12.37	11.43	10.50	9.57
Model_4:	UCL	25.71	24.78	23.85	22.92	21.99	21.06	20.13	19.20
	LCL	6.47	5.54	4.60	3.67	2.74	1.81	.88	-.05
S5-	Forecast	14.45	13.23	12.02	10.81	9.59	8.38	7.17	5.95
Model_5:	UCL	23.60	22.46	21.33	20.19	19.06	17.92	16.78	15.65
	LCL	5.30	4.01	2.71	1.42	.13	-1.16	-2.45	-3.74
S6-	Forecast	19.57	18.67	17.78	16.88	15.98	15.08	14.18	13.29
Model_6:	UCL	25.32	24.45	23.58	22.71	21.84	20.97	20.10	19.23
	LCL	13.82	12.90	11.97	11.04	10.12	9.19	8.27	7.34
S7-	Forecast	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13
Model_7:	UCL	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74
	LCL	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52
S8-	Forecast	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65
Model_8:	UCL	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66
	LCL	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64
S9-	Forecast	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13
Model_9:	UCL	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22
	LCL	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96
S10-	Forecast	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23
Model_10:	UCL	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13
	LCL	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66
S11-	Forecast	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48
Model_11:	UCL	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02
	LCL	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94

Figure 3.22. Graphical prediction analysis for I14

Net business situation: establishment rate + termination rate – percentage

The related descriptive analysis S1 presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. at Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentiles 25, 50, 75, so 23.4178, 2.35775, 19.8700, 7.07325, 50.031, 1.257, .717, 1.154, 1.400, 21.33, 16.89, 38.22, 17.080, 18.05, 08.090, 18.05

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 Holt; S4 - Model_4 Holt; S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 Holt; S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .343, .475, -9.548E-15, . 959, -9.548E-15, -8.615E-15; R-square .194, .283, -9.548E-15, .730, -9.548E-15, -8.615E-15; RMSE 11,114, 15,344, 2,432, 55,463, 2,432, 2,634; MAPS 26,794, 25,514, 7,195, 99,571, 7,195, 7,941; MaxAPE 63,536, 65,030, 13,757, 249,061, 13,757, 16,840; MAE 7,281, 8,854, 1,758, 32,746, 1,758, 1,925; MaxAE

25,858, 42,034, 3,526, 147,356, 3,526, 3,815; Normalized BIC 4.195, 1.724, 2.266, 8.276, 2.266, 2.356.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following overall picture for I15 (values presented in the following order - Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: -4.885E-15, -4.885E-15, 7.073 , 23,966, 5,611; S2-Model_2: -9.548E-15, -9.548E-15, 3.440, 16.415, 3.028; S3-Model_3: .936, .730, 4.164, 10.926, 2.592; S4-Model_4: .940, .351, 4.070, 14.634, 2.981; S5-Model_5: .959, .476, 3.869, 13.467, 2.683; S6-Model_6: .933, .574, 2.432, 7.195, 1.758; S7-Model_7: 4.108E-15, 4.108E-15, 11.107, 24.458, 7.776; S8-Model_8: 2.220E-15, 2.220E-15, 4.775, 20.226, 3.793; S9-Model_9: .000, .000, 17,384, 36,106, 10,408; S10-Model_10: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 55.463, 99.571, 32.746; S11-Model_11: -2.665E-15, -2.665E-15, 8.474, 27.765, 6.721.

Table 32. Prediction analysis for I15

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42
	UCL	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73
	LCL	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60
	UCL	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53
	LCL	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67

S3- Model_3:	Forecast	17.05	14.90	12.74	10.59	8.44	6.29	4.14	1.99
	UCL	26.89	24.93	22.96	20.99	19.02	17.05	15.07	13.09
	LCL	7.20	4.86	2.52	.19	-2.14	-4.47	-6.79	-9.12
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	16.09	15.16	14.23	13.30	12.37	11.43	10.50	9.57
	UCL	25.71	24.78	23.85	22.92	21.99	21.06	20.13	19.20
	LCL	6.47	5.54	4.60	3.67	2.74	1.81	.88	-.05
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	14.45	13.23	12.02	10.81	9.59	8.38	7.17	5.95
	UCL	23.60	22.46	21.33	20.19	19.06	17.92	16.78	15.65
	LCL	5.30	4.01	2.71	1.42	.13	-1.16	-2.45	-3.74
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	19.57	18.67	17.78	16.88	15.98	15.08	14.18	13.29
	UCL	25.32	24.45	23.58	22.71	21.84	20.97	20.10	19.23
	LCL	13.82	12.90	11.97	11.04	10.12	9.19	8.27	7.34
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13
	UCL	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74
	LCL	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65
	UCL	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66
	LCL	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13
	UCL	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22
	LCL	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23
	UCL	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13
	LCL	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48
	UCL	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02
	LCL	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94

Figure 3.23. Graphical forecasting analysis for I15

References

Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.

Mihai Covaci, Brîndușa Covaci. Negentropy: a sustainable culture of educational leadership. An OCAI model analysis, 19 January 2023, PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square [<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2487757/v1>]

Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.

Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19

Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) Research report 1, Oradea University

European Commission (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665> (Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)